

F·A·A·M facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B464
 Date: 02 July 2009
 Take Off: 13:48:22Z Cranfield
 Landing: 15:38:29Z Cranfield
 Flight Time: 1h 50m 07s

Campaign: TAFTS Test Flight (pre CAVIAR)

Operating Area: East Anglia

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist	Paul Green	Imperial College	
5	Flight Manager	Jamie Trembath	FAAM	Y
6	TAFTS	Ralph Beeby	Imperial College	
7				
8				
9				
10				
11				
12				
13				
14				
15				
16				
17				
18				
19				

Missing Log Sheet	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Sortie De-brief	No debrief appears to have been written
Mission Scientist's log	No log appears to have been taken
ViRC chat log	ViRC not used
TAFTS	No log taken?

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	2 Nov 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The following avi format video recordings should be available at the BADC in core_processed/faam-video :

faam-video-dfc_faam_20090702_r0_b464_135009_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090702_r0_b464_145227_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20090702_r0_b464_135002_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090702_r0_b464_145002_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090702_r0_b464_145220_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090702_r0_b464_134959_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090702_r0_b464_144959_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090702_r0_b464_145218_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20090702_r0_b464_135005_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090702_r0_b464_145224_1hz.avi

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B464

Date:

Project:

Location:

Start Time ----	End Time ----	Event -----	Height (s) -----	Hdg ---	Comments -----
134012		ASP	6.0 kft	058	
134822		T/O	6.0 kft	043	
135637	141748	Run 1	10.0 kft	057	
141821	142833	Profile 1	10.0 - 20.0 kft	253	
142833	144922	Run 2	20.0 kft	260	
144923	150016	Profile 2	20.0 - 30.0 kft	095	
150017	152047	Run 3	30.0 kft	256	
150429		Note	30.0 kft	089	Ignore 03 btwn 150100 and
150300					
153829		Land	0.27 kft	307	
154132		ASP	0.27 kft	307	closed

B464 12:10:55-15:54:24

GLNG_PARA0581, GLAT_PARA0580

Sortie flight B464
2nd July 2009
Pre-CAVIAR test flight

Take off from Cranfield: 1400Z

Land at Cranfield: 1600Z

Aim

To test TAFTS in conditions similar to those to be experienced in CAVIAR 2009 campaign in the Swiss Alps.

Weather Conditions

Near clear sky conditions. Boundary layer cumulus / wispy cirrus are acceptable. No significant rain-bearing cloud.

Sortie

- | | |
|--|-------|
| 1. T/O and transit to Weybourne at FL100. (25mins) | T+25 |
| 2. Profile climb to FL200 (10mins) | T+35 |
| 3. 2x 10 minute runs at FL200, cross wind preferred (25mins) | T+60 |
| 4. Profile climb to FL300 (10mins) | T+70 |
| 5. 2x 10minute runs at FL300, cross wind preferred (25 mins) | T+95 |
| 6. Recover to Cranfield (25mins) | T+120 |
| 7. Land Cranfield 1600Z | |

Key instrument requirements

TAFTS required. ARIES, FWVS if instrument and operate available. No AVAPS required.

B464 - TAFTS/FWVS test flight crew :

1. Captain - Alan Roberts (Directflight)
2. Co-pilot - Ian Ramsay-Rae (Directflight)
3. CCM - Dawn Quinn (Directflight)
4. Mission Scientist 1 / TAFTS1 - Paul Green (Imperial College)
5. Flight Manager - Jamie Trembath (FAAM)
6. Core Chemistry - Doug Anderson (FAAM)
7. TAFTS2 - Ralph Beeby (Imperial College)

Flight:

B464

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problems

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B464
Date: 2 July 2009

Instruments

1. Satcom not working
2. Video Streaming decided it needed to close 14:50:30 restarted 14:51:54
3. and at 15:28:18 not restarted as end of science

Aircraft

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.

Satcom-H Calls

nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) $\frac{1}{4}$ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by: